

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dimethyl fumarate attenuates bile acid retention and liver fibrosis in a mouse model of cholestasis

Hana Lastuvkova,^{1*} Ester Dohnalkova,^{2*} Milos Hroch⁹

¹Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic;

²Department of Biological and Medical Sciences, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic; ³Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic;

⁴Department of Toxicology and Military Pharmacy, Military Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic; ⁵Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Mayo Clinic, Rochester, Minnesota, United States; ⁶Department of Molecular Pathology and Biology, Military Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence in Brno, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic;

⁷Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic; ⁸Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic; and ⁹Department of Medical Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

Abstract

Cholestatic liver diseases are characterized by intrahepatic accumulation of bile acids (BAs), exacerbating liver inflammation, and fibrosis. Dimethyl fumarate (DMF) is a clinically approved anti-inflammatory drug that demonstrated protective effects in several experimental models of liver injury. Still, its effect on BA homeostasis and liver fibrosis has not been thoroughly studied. Herein, we hypothesized that DMF could improve BA homeostasis and mitigate the progression of cholestasis-induced liver fibrosis. The DMF was administered to mice with 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine (DDC)-induced cholestasis for 4 wk. The content of individual BAs in the plasma, liver, bile, intestine, and feces was measured using the LC-MS method alongside the analysis of liver phenotype and related executive and regulatory pathways. The DMF slowed down the progression of DDC-induced liver fibrosis by suppressing hepatic stellate cell and macrophage activation and by reducing c-Jun N-terminal kinase phosphorylation. Notably, DMF reduced BA cumulation in the plasma and liver of cholestatic mice by increasing BA fecal excretion via their reduced *Bacteroidetes* phyla-mediated deconjugation in the intestine. In addition, DMF was identified as the antagonist of the mouse farnesoid X receptor in enterocytes. In conclusion, DMF alleviates DDC-induced cholestatic liver injury through pleiotropic action leading to significant anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic activity of the agent. In addition, DMF mitigates BA retention in the liver and plasma by increasing their fecal excretion in cholestatic mice. These findings suggest that DMF warrants further investigation as a potential therapeutic agent for human chronic fibrosing cholestatic liver disorders.

NEW & NOTEWORTHY Chronic cholestatic cholangiopathies present a therapeutic challenge due to their complex pathophysiology, where the accumulation of bile acids plays a crucial role. In this study, we found that dimethyl fumarate attenuated cholestatic liver damage in a murine model through its significant anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic activity supported by reduced bile acid accumulation in the plasma and liver via their increased fecal excretion.

3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1; 4-dihydrocollidine (DDC); bile acids; cholestasis; dimethyl fumarate; liver fibrosis

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a central pathophysiological mechanism initiating and perpetuating cholestatic liver injury during chronic disorders such as primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) and primary sclerosing cholangitis (PSC). Ongoing bile duct damage

restricts bile secretion, producing intrahepatic accumulation of bile components, particularly bile acids (BAs), which induce hepatocyte death and exacerbate inflammatory response and progressive fibrosis. Bile acids also stimulate the proliferation of atypical ductules, which release proinflammatory and profibrotic mediators, further accelerating liver injury (1). Without

*H. Lastuvkova and E. Dohnalkova contributed equally to this work

Correspondence: S. Micuda (micuda@lfhk.cuni.cz).

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proper therapy, inflammation and fibrosis progress to cirrhosis and end-stage liver disease. Unfortunately, no effective treatment is available for PSC, and only 60% of patients with PBC respond to treatment with ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) (2). Liver transplantation remains the only effective therapeutic option for many patients with end-stage liver disease. Therefore, the discovery of novel therapeutic modalities for these cholangiopathies is highly desired.

Dimethyl fumarate (DMF) is an anti-inflammatory drug approved for the treatment of inflammatory disorders such as psoriasis and multiple sclerosis. The commonly referred mechanism of DMF anti-inflammatory action involves the inactivation of Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (KEAP1), which in turn releases active Nuclear factor E2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) (3). However, other effects have been reported, including interference with autophagy, NLPR3 inflammasome activation, glutathione availability, hydroxycarboxylic acid receptor 2-NF- κ B pathway, and aerobic glycolysis necessary for inflammatory cell activation (3, 4). Besides its direct effect on inflammatory cells, DMF appears to reduce gut permeability and translocation of LPS (lipopolysaccharide) to portal circulation, which prevents activation of Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) in Kupffer cells (KCs) and KC-mediated production of proinflammatory mediators (5). Consequently, DMF improved markers of liver injury in various experimental models of liver disorders, including alcoholic hepatopathy (5, 6), carbon tetrachloride or thioacetamide-induced hepatocellular damage (7, 8), ischemia/reperfusion injury (9, 10), steatosis (11, 12), concanavalin A-induced hepatitis (13), and short-term cholestasis induced by 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine (DDC) diet (14) and bile duct ligation (15). Therefore, DMF deserves further investigation for its potential to suppress chronic cholestatic injury and consequent fibrosis.

Bile acids (BAs) are major components of bile with numerous metabolic functions. However, hydrophobic BAs exhibit significant toxicity at supraphysiological concentrations. Under cholestatic conditions, BAs readily accumulate in the liver, disrupt the blood-biliary barrier, activate cholangiocyte proliferation, and initiate inflammatory and fibrotic responses (1). To mitigate these harmful mechanisms, accumulating BAs trigger feedback inhibition of their synthesis from cholesterol and accelerate metabolic inactivation and biliary secretion through the activation of nuclear transcription factors such as the farnesoid X receptor (FXR). Growing evidence suggests that reducing BA accumulation and interfering with these nuclear receptors attenuates cholestatic liver injury. Activation of the FXR receptor by DMF was recently reported (14), but the effect on BA homeostasis is unknown. Therefore, we tested the hypothesis that DMF ameliorates the progression of chronic cholestasis in a mouse model of DDC-induced cholestasis by modulating liver inflammation and fibrosis, while simultaneously decreasing BA accumulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal Study

All experimental procedures were conducted in 12-wk-old male mice at the Animal Facility of the Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove (Charles University) and were previously approved by the Animal Welfare Body of the Faculty of

Medicine in Hradec Kralove and by the Animal Welfare Body of the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports (approval No. MSMT-40612/2018-2). All animal experiments complied with the EU Directive 2010/63/EU. Three-week-old male C57BL/6J mice were obtained from Velaz (Prague, Czech Republic) and housed in groups of five in ventilated cages at a constant temperature and humidity. At the age of 12 wk, animals were randomly divided into four groups (8 mice in each group) as follows: 1) mice fed a chow diet received oral gavage of 1% methylcellulose solution as a vehicle (CV group), 2) mice fed a chow diet were treated with DMF via oral gavage (25 mg/kg) dissolved in vehicle solution (CD group), 3) mice fed with a diet supplemented with 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine (DDC, Cat. No. NDC112-04 PS M-Z, Test compound diet) and received oral gavage of vehicle (DV group), and 4) mice fed a DDC diet received oral gavage of DMF (25 mg/kg) dissolved in vehicle (DD group). DMF or vehicle (1% methylcellulose) was administered once daily by oral gavage for 4 wk with the diets. All mice finished the experiment. The dose and timing of DMF were selected based on previous studies (7, 16) and upon preliminary testing within the 10–50 mg/kg range (Supplemental Fig. S1). Due to the rapid onset of DDC-induced cholestasis, the DMF was administered since the first day of the DDC diet, which is a limitation of the study. After the final dose of DMF or vehicle, mice were placed individually and stool was collected for 24 h. The mice were then anesthetized with pentobarbital (50 mg/kg, ip), and bile was collected for 30 min through the cannulated gallbladder between 9:00 and 11:00 AM to synchronize with BA production. At the end of the experiment, a blood sample was taken from the inferior vena cava, the animals were euthanized by the cervical dislocation, and organs were harvested. All samples were stored at -80°C until analysis.

Intestinal Permeability Assay

A separate set of C57BL/6J male mice was used to evaluate intestinal permeability. Animals were divided into four groups, and identical diet/dosage regimens were applied as described above ($n = 9$ per group). After 4 wk of DMF/DDC administration, mice were fasted for 4 h and 4-kDa fluorescein isothiocyanate-dextran (FITC dextran, FD4, Sigma-Aldrich, the dose of 600 mg/kg body weight, dissolved in 80 mg/mL phosphate-buffered saline, PBS) was applied orally by gavage as a single dose. One animal from each group received only PBS and served as a reference to subtract background fluorescence for measurements in the cecum and colon. Four hours after FITC-dextran administration, mice were anesthetized by isoflurane inhalation anesthesia, a blood sample was taken from the inferior vena cava for FD4 analysis, the animal was euthanized by the cervical dislocation, and organs were harvested. FD4 fluorescence in plasma was determined by a Tecan Infinite200 plate reader, and concentrations were calculated from the calibration curve prepared in PBS ranging from 0 to 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Cecum and colon content of unabsorbed FITC-dextran (FD4) were measured by IVIS Spectrum In Vivo Imaging System (Perkin-Elmer, Inc., Waltham, MA) by image analysis using Living Image 4.4 software. The system was set to acquire images with a 500 nm excitation filter and a 540 nm emission filter for fluorescence imaging. The content was then expressed as total radiant efficiency.

Histopathological Examination of the Liver

Liver tissue was processed as described recently (17). Briefly, formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded liver sections (4 μm) were stained with hematoxylin and eosin to grade liver injury and with Sirius red to classify fibrosis. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained samples were quantified blindly in 10 random segments using a Nikon Eclipse TE300 with polarized light. Sirius red-stained samples were evaluated using the BX-51 microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) and computer image analysis Image-Pro Plus 7.0 (Media Cybernetics, Bethesda, MD). Microphotographs of 10 randomly selected small-vessel portal triads were taken at a 600-fold original magnification from each mouse sample (light intensity adjustment set at maximum and exposition time of 1 ms). The collagen fibers were detected in the Red/Green/Blue scale (RGB) with the range red 221–254, green 115–208, and blue 149–206. Subsequently, the percentual positivity (%) of stained areas of viewing fields was measured.

Analytical Methods

Plasma activity of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and concentration of bilirubin was detected using a commercial Preventive Care Profile Plus test with a Vetscan 2 device (Abaxis) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The glutathione was measured in its reduced (GSH) and oxidized (GSSG) forms in the liver and bile using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with fluorescence detection (18). The Ccl2 concentration in the medium collected from bone marrow-derived macrophages was analyzed using a Mouse Ccl2/Mcp-1 Quantikine ELISA kit (R&D systems, MN). Samples of plasma, bile, liver, small intestine, and feces for BA analysis were collected and processed as detailed in our previous study (17). Furthermore, the ileum tissue for BA analysis was excised, flushed 2 times with cold saline, cut lengthwise, and washed two times for 3 min in saline to remove the remaining intestinal content. The ileum wall with mucosa was then cut and homogenized in 50% ethanol to extract BAs. The concentration of bile acids (BAs) was measured using a liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) method as described previously (19). Calculations of primary (1 $^\circ$), secondary (2 $^\circ$), 12 α -hydroxylated (12 α), non-12 α -hydroxylated (n12 α), conjugated, and unconjugated BAs were detailed in our recent work (17). The 6-hydroxylated (6) BAs were calculated as the sum of muricholic, hyocholic, and hyodeoxycholic acids; non-6-hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated (n6n12) BAs were the sum of all other non-12 α -hydroxylated BAs. The bile acid pool was calculated as the sum of the total BAs in the enterohepatic circulation, including the liver, small intestine, and biliary system (20). The BA content in the biliary system was estimated from BA biliary secretion over 20 min, corresponding with the average volume of the gallbladder.

Quantification of Gene and Protein Expression in the In Vivo Samples

Total RNA was isolated from the liver and ilea of mice using TRIzol and transcribed to cDNA by a High-Capacity cDNA reverse transcription kit (Life Technologies) (21). The quantitative reverse transcription real-time PCR was performed on a Quantstudio 7 HT Fast Real-Time PCR

System using predesigned TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Supplemental Table S1) and TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA). Relative gene expression was calculated by the standard $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method using 18S ribosomal RNA (18S rRNA) as a housekeeping gene. The Western blot method was used for protein analysis. The primary antibodies used for the immunodetection of proteins are listed in Supplemental Table S2. The bands were detected using Fusion Solo 6S Edge (Vilber Lourmat SAS, Collegien, France). The protein expression was normalized to the total content of protein visualized on the blotting membrane using stain-free technology. The total cellular fraction was used to analyze regulatory kinases in the liver, or crude membrane fraction prepared by differential ultracentrifugation was used for Western blot analysis of BA-related enzymes and transporters in the liver and ileum.

Human Hepatic Stellate Cells

The hepatic stellate cells (HSCs), stellate cell medium with all required supplements, and poly-L-lysine were purchased from ScienCell Research Laboratories (Carlsbad, CA). Cells from the third and fourth passages were used for experiments. HSC cells were grown in poly-L-lysine coated flasks in stellate cell medium supplemented with 2% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 IU/mL penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 at 37°C. After reaching confluence, the cells were cultured for 24 h under the following conditions: 1) medium only (control cells), 2) 3 ng/mL transforming growth factor beta 1 (TGF- β 1; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) to activate a fibrotic phenotype, and 3) 3 ng/mL TGF- β 1 plus 50 μM DMF (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO). After 24 h, total RNA was extracted using the High Pure RNA Isolation Kit (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) and reverse-transcribed into cDNA using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Real-time PCR was done using a Quantstudio 7 HT Fast Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) with predesigned TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Supplemental Table S1) and TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master Mix. Data were normalized to the 18S rRNA gene, and the results were analyzed by the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method. Three independent experiments were performed.

Bone Marrow-Derived Macrophages

The bone marrow-derived macrophages (BMMs) were derived from 6 to 10-wk-old C57BL/6J female mice (Velaz, Czech Republic), as described recently (22). Briefly, dissected femurs and tibias were used to flush bone marrow cells. These cells were differentiated into macrophages in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) supplemented with 10% (vol/vol) fetal bovine serum (FBS, USA origin from Merck), 20% L929-conditioned medium (containing macrophage-colony stimulating factor), and antibiotics—50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin and 50 U/mL penicillin (for the first 3 days of cultivation only) at 37°C and 5% CO_2 . On day 7, the differentiated cells were detached with ice-cold Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS), resuspended in fresh DMEM with 10% FBS, and seeded onto 48-well polystyrene plates in density 250,000 cells/ cm^2 . For M1 polarization, the BMMs were treated with *Escherichia coli* lipopolysaccharide (LPS; Merck, Darmstadt,

Germany) in a concentration of 100 ng/mL for 2 h and consequently with either dexamethasone (1 μ M, positive control) or dimethyl fumarate (10 or 50 μ M). The mRNA was thereafter extracted and processed as described for HSC. Mouse-pre-designed TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Supplemental Table S1) were used. Three independent experiments were performed.

HepaRG

Cryopreserved HepaRG (Gibco) cells and media were obtained from Life Technologies (Carlsbad, CA). The HepaRG cell line was cultured and differentiated as described previously (21). To study interaction at the FXR receptor, cells were treated with OCA (obeticholic acid) 1 μ M and 50 μ M dimethyl fumarate for 48 h. Total RNA was isolated using TRIzol Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and reverse transcription was performed with the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Quantitative PCR was performed using TaqMan Fast Advanced Master Mix with TaqMan probes (*CYP7A1*, *ABCBI1*, *NROB2*, Supplemental Table S1). The $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method was used for gene expression quantification with normalization to 18S gene expression.

GLUTag

Murine GLUTag cells derived from colonic tumors of transgenic mice expressing large T antigen under the control of the proglucagon promoter were kindly provided by Dr. Colette Roche (Centre de Recherche en Cancérologie de Lyon, INSERM U1052, Lyon, France) with the permission of Dr. Daniel J. Drucker (Lunenfeld Tanenbaum Research Institute Mt. Sinai Hospital, Toronto). GLUTag cells were treated with studied compounds: control DMSO 0.1%, OCA 1 μ M, and DMF 50 μ M for 48 h. Total RNA was isolated using TRIzol, and reverse transcription was performed with the RevertAid RT Reverse Transcription Kit. qPCR was performed using TaqMan Fast Advanced Master Mix. Data were normalized to reference genes *B2m* and *Gapdh* and were evaluated by the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method. TaqMan probes for *Fgf15*, *Nr0b2*, and *Slc51b* mouse genes as well as for reference genes *B2m* and *Gapdh* genes were obtained from Thermo Fisher (Supplemental Table S1).

Luciferase Reporter Assays

GLUTag cells were kindly provided as described above. Human hepatocellular carcinoma HepG2 cells were purchased from the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC, Salisbury, UK). The HepG2 and GLUTag cells were cultivated in antibiotic-free Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum at 37°C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. All transient transfection reporter gene assays were performed with Lipofectamine 3000 (Thermo Fisher, Carlsbad, CA). The HepG2 or GLUTag cells were seeded at the density of 40,000 cells/cm² on 48-well plates 24 h before transfection. The cells were transfected with 150 ng/well of a luciferase reporter gene construct (pGL4.35 [luc2P/9XGAL4UAS/Hygro], FXRE-luc, or B-1.6k/PB/XREM) together with 100 ng/well of a corresponding NR expression vector [pCMX-GAL4-hFXR, mFXR (expression vector Clone ID OMu23106 NM_001163700.1 Nr1h4, Genscript), mCAR, CAR3 variant] and 30 ng/well of pRL-TK Renilla luciferase vector 24 h before the treatment. After the 24-h treatment, luciferase

activity was measured from the cell lysate with the Dual Luciferase Reporter Assay System from Promega (Hercules, CA). DMF and MMF (monomethyl fumarate) were used at 10, 25, and 50 μ M concentrations in the experiments together with human CAR (1 μ M, CITCO, 6-(4-chlorophenyl)imidazo[2,1-b][1,3]thiazole-5-carbaldehyde-O-(3,4-dichlorobenzyl)oxime, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) or mouse CAR (10 μ M, TCPOBOP, 1,4-bis-[2-(3,5-dichloropyridyloxy)]benzene, 3,3',5,5'-tetrachloro-1,4-bis(pyridyloxy)benzene, Merck) ligands. Obeticholic acid (1 μ M, OCA, 6-ethylchenodeoxycholic acid, Selleckchem, Cologne, Germany) was used as the farnesoid X receptor ligand. The FXR response elements (FXRE)-driven luciferase reporter plasmid (FXRE-luc) was constructed as we described before (23). CYP2B6-luc reporter plasmid (originally entitled as B-1.6k/PB/XREM) was kindly donated by Dr. Hongbing Wang (University of Maryland School of Pharmacy, Baltimore, MD) and was used in assays with human CAR variant 3 and mouse Car expression vectors (pcDNA3.1 + /C-(K)-DYK vector for CAR variant 3, cloneID OHu34914, XM_005245697.4, Genscript, Piscataway, NJ, and mouse Car expression vector pCMV6-mCar, NM_009803, OriGene Technologies, Rockville, MD) (24). Data are presented as fold changes to vehicle-treated control samples. Experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated at least three times.

Molecular Docking

Docking studies were conducted using the Schrödinger Maestro 14.1 software package. Ligand structures were drawn with ChemDraw 22.2, and their conformations were generated and energy-minimized using the LigPrep tool with the OPLS4 force field. The three-dimensional crystal structure of mCAR (PDB code: 1XLS) was obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. The mCAR receptor was prepared using the Protein Preparation Workflow, which included optimization, charge calculation, deletion of the cocrystal ligand, and addition of hydrogen atoms. Ligand docking at inhibitor binding sites was performed using the GLIDE XP tool for high accuracy (2). Known TCPOBOP was used as a control, and redocking was performed as necessary to confirm the poses.

Gut Microbiota Analysis

Total DNA was isolated from cecum using the QIAamp Fast DNA Stool Mini Kit (QIAGEN, cat. no. 51604) following the manufacturer's protocol. DNA yield and integrity were confirmed using a NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer. Quantitative PCR was performed using a Quantstudio 7 HT Fast-Real Time PCR System with Sybr Select Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA). The 16S rRNA gene-targeted group-specific primers were used to quantify bacteria phyla from *Firmicutes*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Actinobacteria*, and *Proteobacteria*. The primer sequences are listed in Supplemental Table S3. A standard curve of the Universal Eubacteria 16S rRNA gene was used to measure bacterial abundance.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were done using GraphPad Prism 8 statistical software (San Diego, CA). The data distribution was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Data are presented as the median with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively. Statistical

significance ($P < 0.05$) was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. The t test or Mann–Whitney U tests were used if only two groups were compared depending on data distribution.

RESULTS

DMF Alleviates Biochemical and Histological Hallmarks of DDC-Induced Liver Injury

To examine the effect of dimethyl fumarate (DMF) on chronic cholestasis, male C57Bl/6J mice were placed on a diet containing DDC for 4 wk. Simultaneously, mice were treated with daily oral gavage of either DMF (25 mg/kg) or vehicle for 4 wk while continuing the diet. The effect of DMF on the intact liver was assessed by its administration to control chow diet-fed mice. After the feeding period, the DDC diet significantly reduced body weight, whereas DMF had no effect on either control or cholestatic animals (Fig. 1A). The DDC diet significantly increased liver weight and liver-to-body weight ratio compared with vehicle-administered control mice. The DMF did not change these parameters in control or DDC-fed mice relative to corresponding untreated groups (Fig. 1A). The plasma activities of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) were markedly increased in the untreated DDC-fed group (Fig. 1B) as a biochemical marker of hepatocyte injury. The administration of DMF significantly reduced the activity of ALT in cholestatic mice. DMF did not change the ALT activities in the control group receiving the chow diet. Moreover, cholestasis hallmarks in plasma, such as alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity and bilirubin concentrations, were significantly increased in DDC-fed mice (Fig. 1B). Similarly, DMF treatment significantly decreased these increments, whereas no drug effect was detected in control mice. Other biochemical parameters were simultaneously analyzed to exclude significant toxicity of DMF at the dose of 25 mg/kg. None of these parameters were affected by dimethyl fumarate in control or cholestatic mice (Supplemental Fig. S2).

The DDC diet significantly reduced bile flow per gram of the liver compared with control mice (Fig. 1C), and DMF treatment restored this impairment. The significant effect of DMF on the bile flow in the DDC-fed mice was also apparent when it was evaluated as the absolute flow or recalculated to body weight (Supplemental Fig. S3 and Supplemental Table S4). Staining liver sections with hematoxylin-eosin showed healthy parenchyma in chow diet-fed groups (Fig. 1D). The untreated DDC-fed mice showed typical cholestatic injury of liver parenchyma with inflammatory infiltration and markedly proliferated bile ducts (Fig. 1D). Biliary infarcts produced by precipitated crystals of protoporphyrin were also apparent. The DMF administration to the cholestatic group significantly attenuated inflammation and ductular reaction. Altogether, the DMF alleviated DDC-induced liver injury as measured by biochemical and histological parameters.

DMF Reduces Liver Inflammation by Suppressing Bone Marrow-Derived Macrophages

Macrophages are key regulators of the inflammatory response during liver injury. Therefore, we measured proinflammatory

markers in the whole liver and in vitro in activated bone marrow-derived macrophages (Fig. 2). The DDC feeding significantly elevated mRNA levels of *Ccl2*, *Ly6c*, *Il-1 β* , and *Tnf- α* , compared with mice on a chow diet (Fig. 2A), and DMF treatment abrogated this elevation for *Ccl2*, *Ly6c*, *Il1 β* , and *Tnf- α* .

To analyze DMF’s effect on macrophages, we isolated primary mouse bone marrow-derived macrophages from C57Bl/6J mice. Then, cells were activated with LPS (100 μ g/mL) in combination with dexamethasone (1 μ M), a positive anti-inflammatory control, and two concentrations of DMF (10 and 50 μ M) (Fig. 2B). Consistent with the in vivo anti-inflammatory effect, both concentrations of DMF significantly attenuated LPS-mediated increase in *Ccl2* and *Il-1 β* mRNA expressions in macrophages and reduced *Ccl2* concentration in cell culture media (Fig. 2, B and C). These findings suggest that DMF inhibits liver inflammation and macrophage activation in chronic cholestasis induced by the DDC diet.

To evaluate molecular mechanisms of reduced inflammation, we analyzed the liver protein content of active phosphorylated forms of major proinflammatory kinases that regulate ongoing cholestatic liver injury (Fig. 2D). The DDC diet significantly increased the phosphorylation of p38, ERK, and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) compared with controls on the chow diet (Fig. 2D). DMF treatment significantly reduced the phosphorylation of JNK in cholestatic mice, indicating that suppression of this pathway represents the major mechanism by which DMF suppresses DDC-induced inflammation.

DMF Attenuates DDC-Induced Liver Fibrosis

Because liver fibrosis is the central issue associated with long-term cholestasis, indicating a transition to a severe form of liver injury, we examined fibrotic changes in liver parenchyma and hepatic stellate cell activation (Fig. 3). The mRNA expression of *Acta2*, a marker of HSC conversion into myofibroblasts, was significantly increased by DDC feeding. The DMF administration significantly attenuated *Acta2* expression in cholestatic mice (Fig. 3A). Similarly, elevated mRNA levels of collagen *Coll1a1* and *Coll1a2* detected in untreated cholestatic animals were significantly decreased with DMF treatment (Fig. 3A).

Then, we measured the mRNA expression of a marker related to extracellular matrix accumulation, *Timp1*, which was significantly increased by the DDC diet. Treatment with DMF significantly decreased *Timp1* expression compared with the untreated DDC-fed group (Fig. 3A). To confirm these data at the protein level, we stained the liver sections with Sirius red to visualize collagen deposition. Figure 3B presents representative images of chow and DDC-fed mice along with corresponding groups treated with DMF. Image analysis of collagen content in small-vessel portal triads revealed that collagen staining was significantly enhanced in DDC-fed mice. Meanwhile, DMF treatment reduced the extent of collagen deposition compared with untreated cholestatic mice (Fig. 3B).

To further elucidate the effects of DMF on liver fibrosis, we activated human hepatic stellate cells with TGF β 1 and treated them with DMF (50 μ M). Consistent with in vivo data, we found that DMF abrogated the inducing effect of TGF β 1 on

Figure 1. Dimethyl fumarate reduces DDC-induced liver damage. **A:** at the end of the experiment, the mouse body and liver weights were determined and the liver-to-body weight ratio was calculated. **B:** DMF significantly reduced plasma alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activities and bilirubin concentrations in the DDC-fed group. **C:** DMF attenuated bile flow reduction by the DDC diet. **D:** hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) staining ($\times 40$ and $\times 100$ magnifications) showed that DMF alleviated pericholangitis and ductular reaction in response to DDC feeding; scale bar, 100 μm . Black arrowheads indicate inflammatory cell infiltration. White arrowheads indicate ductular proliferation. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group). $**P < 0.01$; $***P < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice; $††P < 0.01$, $†††P < 0.001$ DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice. DDC, 0.1% 3,5-dithoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate.

the mRNA expression of *ACTA2* and *COL1A1* (Fig. 3C). In line with the attenuated fibrosis, DMF administration significantly decreased the intensity of DDC-induced ductular proliferation, as evidenced by a reduction in mRNA expression of *Krt19* and *Foxm1*, respectively, compared with untreated DDC-fed mice (Fig. 3D). Taken together, these results suggest that DMF ameliorates DDC-induced liver fibrosis by suppressing HSC activity while simultaneously attenuating the ductular reaction.

Nuclear Factor (Erythroid-Derived 2)-Related Factor 2 (Nrf2) Is Not Fully Responsible for the Protective Effect of DMF on Chronic DDC-Induced Liver Injury

Several recent studies suggested that the anti-inflammatory effects of DMF are mediated by its ability to covalently succinate Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (KEAP1), which activates Nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-related factor 2 (Nrf2) (25). To further investigate the contribution of

this mechanism to the protective effect of DMF observed in our study, we measured the mRNA expression of the Nrf2 target gene in the livers of DMF-treated mice as well as in bone marrow-derived macrophages and human hepatic stellate cells in vitro (Fig. 4). The DDC diet robustly increased the hepatic mRNA expression of *Hmox1*, *Nqo1*, *Gclm*, and *Gpx2* (Fig. 4A). Notably, DMF did not change the mRNA

content of these four genes in the liver of animals receiving either chow or DDC diet compared with their respective vehicle-administered groups (Fig. 4A).

In agreement, DMF did not alter liver concentrations of reduced glutathione (GSH), the major free radical scavenger, which significantly increased in the DDC diet group compared with the chow diet groups. Glutathione also accumulated in

the liver in the oxidized form (GSSG) (Fig. 4B). Therefore, the ratio of reduced to oxidized glutathione, another indicator of oxidative stress, was not changed either by the DDC diet or DMF administration. The DDC diet significantly reduced biliary glutathione secretion per gram of the liver in mice, and DMF treatment did not affect this parameter (Fig. 4C, Supplemental Table S5). To eliminate the potentially confusing effect of increased liver weight in DDC-fed groups, we also evaluated glutathione biliary secretion as the absolute value or recalculated to body weight (Supplemental Fig. S3 and Supplemental Table S5). This evaluation yielded similar results confirming the cholestatic effect of DDC and the tendency toward an increase in DMF-treated DDC-fed mice.

The involvement of Nrf2 signaling in the DMF effect was also evaluated in vitro in bone marrow-derived macrophages (Fig. 4D), where LPS increased the mRNA of *Hmox1*, *Nqo1*, *Gclm*, and *Gclc*. The addition of dexamethasone as a positive anti-inflammatory control or two DMF concentrations to media further increased mRNA expression of *Hmox1*, reduced that of *Nqo1*, did not modify mRNA of *Gclm*, and variably changed *Gclc* when DMF at 10 μ M increased the *Gclc* mRNA. In contrast, DMF significantly increased the expression of *NQO1*, *HMOX1*, *GCLM*, and *GCLC* in human hepatic stellate cells activated by TGF β 1 (Fig. 4E). The discrepancies in changes of measured target genes suggest that Nrf2 activation is not the principal mechanism of DMF protective action against DDC-induced inflammatory reaction. However, Nrf2 activation by DMF may play a role in attenuating the profibrotic response of hepatic stellate cells.

DMF Reduces Plasma Concentrations and Liver Content of Bile Acids in DDC-Fed Mice

BA homeostasis has not been comprehensively characterized in the DDC model of cholestasis concerning the analysis of BA spectra and enterohepatic recycling. Hydrophobic BAs are hepatotoxic compounds that significantly accumulate during cholestasis and promote liver inflammation and fibrosis. Therefore, we analyzed BA profiles in the plasma and enterohepatic compartment, where they are mainly concentrated. The values measured for individual BAs and their groups differ by several orders of magnitude; therefore, a logarithmic scale is used for graphical presentation. The individual values are then presented in the attached Supplemental Tables S6–S8. Total plasma concentrations of BAs were significantly increased in DDC-fed mice compared with those fed a chow diet (Fig. 5A). This increase was due to the accumulation of 12 α -hydroxylated, 6-hydroxylated,

non-6/non-12 α -hydroxylated, primary, conjugated, and unconjugated BAs. Cholestatic animals exhibited a significant decrease in the plasma ratio of 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BAs and an increase in primary/secondary and conjugated/unconjugated BA ratios. The DMF administration significantly reduced total BAs in the plasma of cholestatic animals because of proportional 12 α -hydroxylated, 6-hydroxylated, primary, and conjugated BAs reduction. The DMF increased plasma ratios of 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BAs in control mice, but it did not change BA ratios in cholestatic mice (Fig. 5A).

The liver BA content in untreated DDC-fed animals demonstrated a similar pattern of changes as those observed in plasma, that is, total BAs were increased compared with mice on a chow diet. Vehicle-administered cholestatic mice exhibited liver accumulation of 6-hydroxylated, primary, and conjugated BAs with a markedly reduced ratio of 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BAs and an increase in primary/secondary and conjugated/unconjugated BA ratios. In comparison, DMF reduced the BA amount in the liver of cholestatic animals (Fig. 5B). DMF treatment of DDC-fed mice significantly reduced primary and conjugated BAs with subsequent reduction in primary/secondary and conjugated/unconjugated BA ratios.

Interestingly, identical patterns of changes have been measured for BA biliary secretion and BA small intestine content (Fig. 5, C and D). For both parameters, the total BAs were significantly reduced in vehicle-administered DDC-fed mice relative to control mice on chow diet, mainly due to significantly decreased 12 α -hydroxylated, non-6/non-12 α -hydroxylated, primary, secondary, conjugated but also unconjugated BAs. These changes significantly reduced 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BA ratios and increased primary/secondary BA ratios. The conjugated/unconjugated BA ratio was significantly increased in the bile of vehicle-administered DDC-fed mice. Importantly, DMF did not modify either of these parameters in control or cholestatic mice, except for significantly increased biliary and intestinal ratio of 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BAs in control mice (Fig. 5, C and D).

To eliminate the potentially confusing effect of recalculating BA biliary secretion to liver weight, which was significantly increased in DDC-fed groups, we also evaluated BA biliary secretion as the absolute value and relative to body weight (Supplemental Fig. S4 and Supplemental Table S7). The DDC-fed mice had a reduction of absolute biliary

Figure 2. DMF ameliorated hepatic inflammation in DDC-fed mice. A: quantitative reverse transcription real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) was used to measure the mRNA expressions of *Ccl2*, *Ly6c*, *Il-1 β* , and *Tnf- α* in the liver. B: the mRNA expression of *Ccl2* and *Il-1 β* was induced in bone marrow-derived macrophages activated with bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS), and DMF presence in the medium attenuated this induction. Dexamethasone (Dex) was used as positive anti-inflammatory control. C: DMF reduced concentration of *Ccl2* in the medium of bone marrow-derived macrophages activated with LPS. D: the protein expression of phosphorylated mitogen-activated kinases such as p38, ERK, and JNK was measured by Western blot. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group, $n = 3$ for cells). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice (in cells: LPS-treated vs. vehicle-treated macrophages); + $P < 0.05$, ++ $P < 0.01$, +++ $P < 0.001$ DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice (in cells: LPS + DMF vs. LPS-treated macrophages). *Ccl2*, the chemokine ligand 2; DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; Dex, dexamethasone; DMF, dimethyl fumarate; ERK, extracellular signal-regulated kinase; *Il-1 β* , Interleukin-1 beta; JNK, c-Jun N-terminal kinase; *Ly6c*, lymphocyte antigen 6 complex; p38, p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase; *Tnf- α* , tumor necrosis factor alpha.

Figure 3. DMF attenuated DDC-induced liver fibrosis. **A:** DMF reduced DDC-activated mRNA expression of *Acta2*, *Col1a1*, *Col1a2*, and *Timp1* as determined by quantitative reverse transcription real-time PCR (qRT-PCR). **B:** Sirius red staining shows ($\times 40$ and $\times 100$ magnifications) that collagen deposition was significantly reduced in DMF-treated DDC-fed mice. Scale bar, 100 μm . **C:** DMF reduced activation of primary human stellate cells as demonstrated by reduced mRNA expression of *ACTA2* and *COL1A1*. **D:** DMF mitigated liver ductular proliferation in DDC-fed mice, as verified by reduced mRNA expression of the *Krt19* and *Foxm1* markers. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group, $n = 4$ for cells). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice (in cells: TGF- β -treated vs. vehicle-treated hepatic stellate cells); † $P < 0.05$, †† $P < 0.01$, ††† $P < 0.001$ DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice (in cells: TGF- β + DMF vs. TGF- β -treated hepatic stellate cells). DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate.

secretion of total BA, while recalculation to BW, which was reduced by DDC, masked this difference. Both additional ways of BA biliary excretion showed significant reduction of 12 α -hydroxylated, non-6/non-12 α -hydroxylated, secondary, and unconjugated BA by DDC diet, leading to significant reduction of 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated

BA ratios and increased primary/secondary BA and conjugated/unconjugated ratios. DMF did not change these parameters in control or cholestatic animals (Supplemental Fig. S4).

Ileum tissue content of BAs as an indicator of their active reabsorption was significantly reduced in vehicle-administered

DDC-fed animals in comparison with control mice due to the reduced content of all BA groups except for unconjugated BAs (Fig. 5E). The ratios of BA groups were not modified by the DDC diet. DMF significantly reduced the ileum wall content of BAs in control mice, but the drug did not modify this parameter in DDC-fed mice.

DMF Reduced Especially Plasma and Liver Content of Muricholic Acid

Individual BAs differ in lipid solubility, with hydrophobic BAs being toxic to tissues. Accordingly, we analyzed the concentrations of individual BAs using the LC-MS method.

A

B

C

D Mouse bone marrow-derived macrophages

E Human hepatic stellate cells

Compared with mice on a chow diet, DDC feeding significantly increased plasma concentrations of α MCA, β MCA, GCA, TCDCA, TMCA, TCA, and THCA but reduced concentrations of secondary BAs such as UDCA, DCA, THDCA, and TDCA (Fig. 6A, Supplemental Table S8A). DMF administration to cholestatic animals significantly reduced plasma concentrations of TMCA and GCA. The BA abundance in the liver was increased in DDC-fed animals due to significantly increased content of TMCA, whereas the presence of secondary BAs such as α MCA, TLCA, TUDCA, THDCA, and TDCA was reduced (Fig. 6B, Supplemental Table S8B). Like plasma concentrations, DMF administration also significantly reduced the liver content of TMCA in DDC-fed mice. DDC feeding also markedly reduced the biliary secretion relative to the liver weight of α MCA, β MCA, CA, GCA, TLCA, TUDCA, THDCA, TCDCA, TDCA, and TCA compared with healthy controls (Fig. 6C, Supplemental Table S8C). DMF did not modify the biliary secretion of either BA. A similar influence of DDC was identified when BA biliary secretion was expressed as absolute values while relation to body weight masked some of these changes (Supplemental Fig. S4 and Supplemental Table S7).

Consistent with the biliary secretion of BAs, the small intestine content of BAs (Fig. 6D, Supplemental Table S8D), their major reservoir in the organism, was significantly reduced in DDC-fed animals relative to healthy mice due to significantly reduced presence of α MCA, CA, DCA, GCA, TLCA, TUDCA, THDCA, TCDCA, TDCA, and TCA (Fig. 6D). DMF did not change BA abundance in the small intestine of either control or cholestatic mice, except for an increase in the small intestinal content of TCA in control animals. Reduced BA content in the intestinal system of DDC-fed mice was associated with significantly decreased ileum tissue content of GCA, TUDCA, THDCA, TCDCA, TDCA, TMCA, TCA, and THCA compared with control mice. The DMF treatment did not change the ileum tissue individual BA content, but it reduced GCA, TUDCA, TMCA, TCA, and THCA in control animals (Fig. 6E, Supplemental Table S8E).

DMF Does Not Change the Total BA Pool Reduced by DDC Feeding

The total pool of bile acids refers to the sum of their content in the liver, biliary system, and small intestine. The BA content in the biliary tract was calculated from their biliary secretion over 20 min, corresponding to the average gallbladder volume. DDC-fed mice had a significantly reduced

total BA pool compared with the untreated healthy group, primarily due to a reduction of 12 α -hydroxylated, non-6/non-12 α -hydroxylated, primary, secondary, conjugated, and unconjugated BAs (Supplemental Fig. S5A and Supplemental Table S9A). These differences resulted in a significantly decreased 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated and increased primary/secondary BA ratios in cholestatic animals (Supplemental Fig. S5A). DMF administration significantly increased the 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BA ratio in control mice and attenuated the DDC-induced increase in the primary/secondary BAs ratio in cholestatic mice (Supplemental Fig. S5A). The DDC-fed mice exhibited a significantly reduced pool of UDCA, HDCA, CDCA, DCA, α MCA, CA, GCA, TLCA, TUDCA, THDCA, TCDCA, TDCA, and TCA (Supplemental Fig. S5B). DMF did not alter either of those BA pools in cholestatic animals; however, it increased the content of TCA in animals on the chow diet (Supplemental Fig. S5B and Supplemental Table S9B).

The Effect of DMF on the Expression of BA-Related Genes in the Liver and Ileum

To address the mechanism of changes in BA metabolome and enterohepatic recycling, we analyzed the expression of responsible regulators, enzymes, and transporters in the liver (Fig. 7). As expected, DDC-mediated cholestasis significantly reduced mRNA of the bile salt export pump (*Abcb11* gene, Bsep protein), the rate-limiting transporter for biliary secretion of BAs; the sodium-taurocholate cotransporting polypeptide (*Slc10a1* gene, Ntcp protein), the principal transporter for BA import from sinusoidal blood into hepatocytes; *Cyp8b1*, the major enzyme for 12 α -hydroxylated BA synthesis; *Cyp7b1/Cyp27a1*, enzymes important in non-12 α -hydroxylated BA synthesis; *Cyp2c70*, the enzyme required for the synthesis of muricholic acid; and *Nr0b2* encoding small heterodimer partner, a suppressor transcription factor regulated by FXR receptor. In contrast, the DDC diet significantly induced liver expression of constitutive androstane receptor (Car)-sensitive genes, including *Cyp2b10*, *Cyp3a11*, multidrug resistance-associated protein 2 (*Abcc2* gene for Mrp2 protein), and multidrug resistance-associated protein 4 (*Abcc4* gene for Mrp4 protein), both of which are transporting proteins responsible for the transport of anions such as sulfate and gluconic acid conjugates as well as BAs. DDC also significantly induced mRNA of *Abcb1a/b* encoding Mdr1 drug transporting protein. Of all

Figure 4. DMF influenced variably the expression of Nrf2 target genes and glutathione status in the liver. **A:** DMF did not modify liver mRNA expression of Nrf2 target genes such as *Hmox1*, *Nqo1*, *Gclm*, and *Gpx2* in chow or DDC diet-fed mice. **B:** DMF therapy did not change the liver GSH and GSSG contents and their ratio. **C:** DMF did not modify glutathione biliary secretion. **D:** bone marrow-derived macrophages were activated by lipopolysaccharide. DMF in the medium increased the mRNA expression of *Hmox1*, reduced the mRNA expression of *Nqo1*, unaffected the mRNA content of *Gclm*, and variably modulated *Gclc*. **E:** human hepatic stellate cells were activated by TGF β 1, and DMF addition to medium increased mRNA of Nrf2 target genes such as *NQO1*, *HMOX1*, *GCLM*, and *GCLC*. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group, $n = 3$ for cells). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice (in cells: LPS-treated vs. vehicle-treated macrophages or TGF- β -treated vs. vehicle-treated hepatic stellate cells); + $P < 0.05$, ++ $P < 0.01$, +++ $P < 0.001$ DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice (in cells: LPS + DMF vs. LPS-treated macrophages or TGF- β + DMF vs. TGF- β -treated hepatic stellate cells). DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate; Gclc, Glutamate-Cysteine Ligase Catalytic Subunit; Gclm, Glutamate-cysteine ligase regulatory subunit; Gpx2, Glutathione peroxidase 2; GSH, reduced glutathione; GSSG, oxidized glutathione; Hmox1, heme oxygenase 1; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; Nqo1, NAD(P)H quinone oxidoreductase.

Figure 5. DMF reduced plasma concentrations and liver content of bile acids. Plasma concentrations (A), liver content (B), biliary secretion (C), small intestinal content (D), and ileum tissue content (E) of the main BA groups and their ratios were analyzed in mice. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group). * $P < 0.05$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice; † $P < 0.05$, DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice. DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate. BA groups: sum of all BAs (Σ), 12 α -hydroxylated BAs (12α), 6-hydroxylated (6), non-6-hydroxylated non-12-hydroxylated BAs (n6n12), primary BAs (1°), secondary BAs (2°), taurine/glycine-conjugated BAs (C), and unconjugated BAs (U).

these molecules, DMF attenuated *Cyp2b10*, *Abcc2*, and *Abcc4* expression in cholestatic animals (Fig. 7).

Therefore, we tested the influence of DMF and its major active metabolite, MMF, on human and mouse CAR receptors using gene reporter assays (Supplemental Fig. S6). Among the two, DMF significantly stimulated human CAR activity at the highest concentration of 50 μ M (Supplemental Fig. S6, A and B), whereas MMF had no effect. Furthermore, DMF potentiated human CAR

agonistic activity of the prototype inducer CITCO (Supplemental Fig. S6C), whereas MMF antagonized it at 10 μ M concentration and potentiated it at 50 μ M concentration. Both DMF and MMF showed a tendency toward the potentiation of mouse CAR activated by its agonist TCPOBOP (Supplemental Fig. S6D). Therefore, we performed docking studies with mouse CAR. MMF and DMF directly interact and form H-bonds with the polar residue N175, a key residue for mediating ligand-induced

Figure 6. DMF influences the homeostasis of muricholic and cholic acids. Plasma concentrations (A), liver content (B), biliary secretion (C), small intestinal content (D), and ileum tissue content (E) of individual BAs were analyzed in mice. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group). * $P < 0.05$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice; † $P < 0.05$, DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice. DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate.

activity in mCAR (Supplemental Fig. S6E). TCPOBOP does not form strong H-bonds but engages in other hydrophobic interactions (Supplemental Fig. S6F). The superimposed structures of TCPOBOP with MMF or DMF show that the ligand-binding pocket can accommodate DMF without any clashes. However, a clash with MMF may lead to steric hindrance, causing unfavorable interactions (Supplemental Fig. S6G). These observations may

explain the mechanistic basis of the co-stimulation of mouse CAR activation with TCPOBOP and DMF.

Most of these changes in mRNA were followed by similar changes in the expression of the proteins they encode (Fig. 7A). DDC led to a significant reduction in the protein content of Bsep, Ntcp, Cyp8b1, Cyp7b1, Cyp27a1, Cyp2b10, and Cyp2c70, and to an induction of Mrp4 and Mdr1. DMF administration significantly reduced Cyp2b10 protein in

Figure 7. DMF modified the expression of bile acid-related molecules in the liver. The mRNA (A) and protein (B) expression were analyzed in the liver by quantitative reverse transcription real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) and Western blot, respectively. Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak’s post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn’s post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively ($n = 8$ mice/group). * $P < 0.05$ vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice; † $P < 0.05$, DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice. DDC, 0.1% 3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate.

mice with DDC-induced cholestasis, and Bsep protein in control animals (Fig. 7B).

DMF Increased BA Fecal Excretion

The fecal excretion of total BAs was significantly reduced in cholestatic mice administered with a vehicle compared with control mice (Supplemental Fig. S7 and Supplemental Table S10). As for the DDC-fed mice, all BA groups showed significant decreases: 12 α -hydroxylated, 6-hydroxylated, non-6/non-12 α -hydroxylated, primary, secondary, conjugated, and

unconjugated BAs such as LCA, HDCA, DCA, β MCA, TMCA, TCA, and CA. Consequently, the 12 α -hydroxylated/non-12 α -hydroxylated BA ratio significantly decreased, whereas primary/secondary and conjugated/unconjugated BA ratios significantly increased in DDC-fed mice compared with controls (Supplemental Fig. S7). DMF significantly increased in DDC-fed mice the fecal excretion of total, 12 α -hydroxylated, 6-hydroxylated, primary, conjugated, and unconjugated BAs such as CA, β MCA, TMCA, and TCA, with a significant increase in primary/secondary and conjugated/unconjugated BA ratios (Fig. 8, A and B, Supplemental Table S10).

Figure 8. DMF increased fecal excretion of bile acids in DDC-fed mice. **A:** major BA groups and BA ratios were calculated from the measurement of individual BA by LC-MS in the stool collected over 24 h. **B:** fecal excretion of individual BAs. **C:** the mRNA expression of farnesoid X receptor (FXR)-regulated genes mediating BA reabsorption in the ileum. **D:** protein expression of transporters mediating BA reabsorption in the ileum. **E:** plasma fluorescein isothiocyanate dextran concentrations of the in vivo gut permeability assay. **F:** major bacterial phyla were measured in cecum by quantitative reverse transcription real-time PCR (qRT-PCR). Animal labeling: CV (chow diet with the vehicle), CD (chow diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally), DV (DDC diet with the vehicle), and DD (DDC diet with DMF, 25 mg/kg orally). Statistical significance in fecal excretion between DV and DD groups was evaluated by *t* test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Mann–Whitney *U* test with Dunn's post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a nonnormal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Statistical significance for comparison of more groups was determined using either a one-way ANOVA with Holm–Sidak's post hoc test for data with Gaussian distribution or the Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis with Dunn's post hoc test if at least one mouse group demonstrated a non-normal distribution for the evaluated parameter. Data are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles, respectively (*n* = 8 mice/group). **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, and ****P* < 0.001 vs. vehicle-administered chow diet-treated mice; †*P* < 0.05, DMF-treated vs. vehicle-treated DDC-fed mice. DDC, 0.1% 3,5-dithoxycarbonyl-1,4-dihydrocollidine diet; DMF, dimethyl fumarate, sum of all BAs (Σ), 12 α -hydroxylated BAs (12 α), 6-hydroxylated (6), non-6-hydroxylated non-12-hydroxylated BAs (n6n12), primary BAs (1 $^\circ$), secondary BAs (2 $^\circ$), taurine/glycine-conjugated BAs (C), and unconjugated BAs (U).

Therefore, we analyzed the expression of BA transporters in the ileum as the major mechanism for BA intestinal reabsorption. DDC feeding significantly repressed mRNA expression of FXR receptor-regulated genes such as *Slc51a/b* (*Ost α / β* protein), which are transporters for BA export from enterocytes to the interstitium, *Fabp6* (*Ibapb* protein), an intracellular carrier of BAs, *Fgf15*, and *Nr0b2* regulatory factors (Fig. 8C). The gene expression of *Slc10a2* encoding a sodium/bile acid cotransporter (*Asbt*), the major transporter of BAs from the intestinal lumen into enterocytes was not modified by the DDC diet (Fig. 8C). These changes indicate a reduction in BA reabsorption from the ileum and reflect the organism's attempts to limit the availability of accumulating bile acids

during cholestasis. Interestingly, DMF treatment significantly repressed the *Slc51a/b* transporter in healthy animals, which indicates interference with FXR signaling. Protein analysis of these molecules confirmed significant downregulation of *Ost α* and *Ibapb* in DDC-fed groups, and DMF significantly reduced protein expression of *Ost β* in cholestatic animals (Fig. 8D). Sample pictures of Western blots are exemplified in Supplemental Fig. S8.

BA intestinal reabsorption may also be modified by intestinal permeability. We analyzed this parameter using FITC-dextran. The DDC diet significantly increased FITC-dextran plasma concentrations in DDC-fed groups 4 h after its oral administration, indicating impaired intestinal

barrier. DMF had no effect in this test (Fig. 8E). In addition, we also evaluated unabsorbed FITC-dextran in the cecum and colon using IVIS Spectrum to scan the total fluorescence of organs (Supplemental Fig. S9). Compared with control groups, the DDC diet significantly reduced FITC dextran content in both parts of the large intestine. DMF increased the colon content of FITC dextran in control and DDC-fed mice. In contrast, DMF significantly reduced cecum content in control mice but did not affect content in DDC-fed mice.

A significant increase of primary-to-secondary BAs in all compartments indicated marked changes in intestinal microbiome in DDC-fed groups. The analysis of major bacterial phyla revealed a substantial reduction of *Bacteroidetes* and *Actinobacteria* and a notably increased presence of *Proteobacteria* in DDC-fed groups compared with the vehicle-administered control group (Fig. 8F). DMF therapy in control mice significantly increased the abundance of *Firmicutes* and reduced *Bacteroidetes*. DMF in DDC-fed animals resulted in a further reduction in *Bacteroidetes* and an increase in *Actinobacteria*. These results suggest significant alteration of the intestinal microbiome due to DDC feeding and its modulation by DMF therapy.

DMF Reduces FXR Activity in Cellular Models

DMF reduced some FXR target genes in the ileum of control animals. Therefore, we analyzed the influence of DMF and its metabolite MMF on FXR activity. Obeticholic acid (OCA) was used as a reference FXR agonist. At first, we tested the influence of DMF on the expression of FXR-target genes. The OCA predictably increased mRNA expression of *Fgf15* and *Nr0b2* in GLUTag cells (Fig. 9A), significantly increased *ABCB11* and *NROB2*, and repressed *CYP7A1* expressions in HepaRG cells (Supplemental Fig. S10A). DMF significantly repressed *Fgf15* and *Nr0b2* mRNA in GLUTag cells (Fig. 9A) and increased *CYP7A1* expression in HepaRG cells (Supplemental Fig. S10A). Furthermore, we tested the agonism and antagonism of DMF and MMF at the FXR receptor using human (h) and mouse (m) FXR gene reporters. OCA predictably activated FXR in both cell lines (Fig. 9, B–E, and Supplemental Fig. S10, B–E). We identified that only MMF significantly suppressed the spontaneous activity of mouse gene reporter in GLUTag cells (Fig. 9C) but not in HepG2 cells (Supplemental Fig. S10, B and C), whereas DMF stimulated mouse FXR in HepG2 cells (Supplemental Fig. S10C). Simultaneously, MMF significantly reduced human and mouse FXR activity stimulated by OCA in GLUTag cells (Fig. 9, D and E). MMF also reduced the OCA-induced activity of mouse FXR in HepG2 cells (Supplemental Fig. S10E). At the same time, DMF showed a significant antagonistic effect only at mouse FXR activity in GLUTag cells (Fig. 9E). These results indicate that MMF may especially antagonize mouse and human FXR activity in the intestinal cells.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that DMF alleviates BA accumulation in the plasma and liver of mice with DDC-induced cholestasis. BAs increase during cholestasis and are among

the principal promoters of hepatic inflammation, fibrosis, and ductular proliferation. Consistent with previous studies, we detected a marked increase in BA plasma concentrations (26–28) and liver content (27, 29, 30) in DDC-fed mice. Using detailed BA analysis in the enterohepatic compartment, we demonstrated that DMF mainly reduces primary BAs in cholestatic mice, at least in part by increasing fecal excretion of (T) β MCA and (T)CA. However, we did not detect appropriate changes in the ileum expression of BA reabsorbing transporters regulated by the FXR receptor. Recent studies suggest that activation of the FXR receptor may be a possible mechanism underlying the protective effects of DMF in mice fed with DDC over 2 wk (14). However, the liver FXR target genes, such as *Abcb11* or *Nr0b2*, were not modified by DMF in our DDC-fed mice after 4-wk administration. In contrast, DMF significantly reduced the expression of FXR target genes such as *Slc51a* and *Slc51b* in the ileum of control mice, suggesting FXR antagonism. We consequently confirmed that MMF, the major active metabolite of DMF, is an inhibitor of FXR using reporter assays, preferably in intestinal GLUTag cells. Interestingly, DMF/MMF did not interfere *in vivo* with liver FXR signaling, which may result from interaction with different pathways. These data indicate that FXR activation may not be crucial for the antifibrotic effect of DMF at the later stage of cholestatic liver impairment and that DMF may interfere with FXR in a tissue-dependent manner.

DDC diet caused a reduction in bile flow and BA biliary secretion in response to the downregulation of BA transporters *Bsep* and *Ntcp*. Together with the reduced expression of BA synthesizing enzymes such as *Cyp8b1*, this represents a typical anti-cholestatic response driven by BAs and proinflammatory cytokines (1). Interestingly, the DDC-fed mice showed an induction of *Abcc2* (*Mrp2*) apical transporter expression, which is typically downregulated during cholestasis. This effect may be attributed to the stimulation of the constitutive androstane receptor (CAR) by the DDC diet (28, 31). In our study, CAR receptor agonism by the DDC was also confirmed by the induction of the prototype target gene, *Cyp2b10*. DMF reduced the DDC-mediated induction of *Cyp2b10* and *Abcc2*, suggesting antagonism at the CAR receptor. Indeed, we confirmed the affinity of DMF toward the CAR receptor with low efficacy, but DMF and MMF costimulated CAR receptor in the presence of agonist. It may indicate that DMF reduced the transcription of CAR downstream genes in our DDC-fed group by decreasing the accumulation of CAR agonists rather than through direct CAR antagonism. Thus, we cannot exclude the possibility that DMF altered the metabolism of DDC. However, the expression of *Cyp3a11*, the major mouse enzyme of *Cyp3a* subfamily responsible for bioactivation of DDC to toxic metabolite, was not modified by DMF. Importantly, Yamazaki et al. (28) previously demonstrated attenuation of DDC-induced liver injury in CAR-knockout animals. Therefore, even indirect reduction of the CAR receptor activity may be one of the mechanisms by which DMF alleviates DDC-induced liver injury.

Our analysis of individual BAs allowed us to calculate BA ratios, revealing that the DDC diet resulted in a markedly increased proportion of primary BA across all compartments. Reduced synthesis of secondary BAs indicates that the DDC diet significantly impairs gut microbiota. Indeed,

Figure 9. DMF suppressed farnesoid X receptor (FXR) activity in GLUTag cells. The mRNA expression of FXR target genes in intestinal GLUTag (A) cells incubated with obeticholic acid (OCA, 1 μ M) and dimethyl fumarate (DMF, 50 μ M) for 48 h. B–E: luciferase gene reporter assays with human (h) and mouse (m) FXR-responsive constructs have been performed on transiently transfected intestinal GLUTag cells. Obeticholic acid (OCA, 1 μ M) was used as a prototype FXR ligand in agonistic (B and C) and antagonistic (D and E) modes. Dimethyl fumarate (DMF) was used at concentrations 10 μ M, 25 μ M, or 50 μ M for 24 h. Data were normalized to Renilla luciferase activity and expressed as fold-activation relative to the control (vehicle-treated) cells. Kruskal–Wallis one-way test with Dunn’s post hoc test was used for statistical analysis. Values are presented as medians with boxes and whiskers representing the interquartile range and 5th–95th percentiles of three independent experiments ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ vs. vehicle-treated controls (Ctrl); + $P < 0.05$, ++ $P < 0.01$ vs. OCA-treated cells.

we confirmed that the DDC diet caused a reduction in the abundance of *Bacteroides* spp. and *Actinobacteria* spp. The *Bacteroides* spp. play a significant role in deconjugating BAs (32), whereas 7-dehydroxylation, the second step in secondary BA synthesis, is presumably carried out by members of the *Firmicutes* phylum. In general, reduced intraluminal BAs favor the growth of *Bacteroides*, whereas increased BAs in the gut lumen expand *Firmicutes* at the expense of *Bacteroides*. Therefore, the reduction of BA intestinal content and fecal excretion in our DDC-fed groups suggests that a decrease in *Bacteroides* spp. abundance is produced by direct DDC toxicity rather than through the alteration in BA intestinal content. DMF exhibits antibacterial activity against individual bacteria such as *E. coli* (33) and *Clostridium perfringens* (34). However,

at the phylum level, it only showed a tendency to increase *Firmicutes* levels in the gut microbiota of mice administered 10 mg/kg (35). Consistent with these reports, the administration of DMF at 25 mg/kg in our study might enhance DMF antibacterial activity, reducing gram-negative *Bacteroidetes* and increasing *Firmicutes* in control mice. These changes were not associated with the modulation of primary/secondary BA ratios, indicating that individual strains responsible for BA conversion were not markedly affected. In contrast, DMF further reduced *Bacteroidetes* spp. and increased *Actinobacteria* spp. in the DDC-fed group, increasing primary to secondary and conjugated to unconjugated BA ratios in stool. Simultaneously, we did not detect DMF-mediated protection against DDC-induced gut barrier dysfunction, which

was reported previously for DMF during ethanol-induced damage (5). This discrepancy may be related to a higher aggressiveness of the DDC diet against gut mucosa. Taken together with data of unchanged ileum BA transporter expression, we suggest that DMF may reduce BAs disposition in plasma and liver with positive consequences on liver injury during cholestasis by increasing fecal excretion of conjugated primary BAs due to impaired metabolism by gut microbiota. The limitation for extrapolation of this mechanism to clinical practice is that we observed changes mainly in muricholic acid, which is not synthesized in humans.

Pathology of chronic cholestatic liver disorders is characterized by complex cellular interactions of hepatocytes with cholangiocytes, HSC, and proinflammatory cells, where various initial factors alter bile flow. Subsequently, increased BAs impair hepatocytes and cholangiocytes, triggering the release of cytokines and cholangiocyte proliferation with their conversion to a “reactive phenotype,” known as ductular reaction (1, 36). Parallel disruption of the intestinal barrier increases the exposure of liver cells to bacterial lipopolysaccharides, further promoting proinflammatory and profibrotic signaling. Lipopolysaccharide-TLR4, growth factor, and cytokine receptors are among crucial pathways activated by these stimuli. By analyzing the major regulatory MAP kinases stimulated by these pathways, we identified inhibition of JNK kinase phosphorylation as the principal change produced by DMF in these cascades. JNK/c-Jun pathway is triggered by cytokines such as TNF- α and BAs and contributes especially to the activation of HSCs and the progression of liver fibrosis (37). Phosphorylation of JNK is significantly increased in mice or human fibrotic liver, especially in fibroblasts. Inhibition of JNK or knockout of JNK1 in mice mainly reduced liver fibrosis (37) and blocked in vitro activation of HSC cells. These data are consistent with inhibition of HSC activation by DMF in our study. However, the role of JNK in regulating other liver cell types is less obvious since aged mice with JNK knockout in hepatocytes or cholangiocytes develop large biliary cysts (38). In contrast, DMF in our study reduced the ductular reaction of cholangiocytes. We were not able to uncover, whether there is a direct effect of DMF on cholangiocytes, but based on significantly reduced BAs in the liver and attenuated inflammation with reduced production of cytokines, including those stimulating cholangiocytes such as IL-1 β and TNF- α , we suggest that this might be an important mechanism reducing also ductular reaction. The direct anti-inflammatory effect of DMF was confirmed in vitro using macrophages. Interestingly, we did not detect consistent activation of the Nrf2 pathway, which is often reported as the principal mechanism for DMF-mediated protection against liver injury (14, 15, 39). The only exception was the selective activation of Nrf2 downstream genes by DMF in vitro in HSC. Therefore, we suggest that complex anti-inflammatory and JNK-related antifibrotic mechanisms play a significant role in the DMF's effect during cholestasis.

The limitation of the study is the absence of an evaluation of DMF's effect in female mice since the DDC model is routinely performed in more sensitive male mice. Based on the demonstration of anti-inflammatory effect of dimethyl fumarate on liver injury in other pathological models using

female mice, such as an experimental model of alcoholic liver disorder (5), we may anticipate that DMF would be similarly effective against cholestatic liver injury in females. This is also supported by the suppressive effect of DMF on macrophages isolated from female mice in our study. In contrast, the effect of DMF in healthy female mice may reflect sex-related discrepancies in BA homeostasis (40) and should be addressed in the future.

In conclusion, our results show significant anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, and antiproliferative effects of DMF in chronic DDC-induced liver injury. The principal mechanism of these effects is the attenuation of macrophage and hepatic stellate cell activation and interference with JNK kinase phosphorylation. DMF also antagonizes excessive CAR receptor stimulation caused by the DDC diet and alters gut microbiota, reducing deconjugation and metabolism of BAs and increasing their fecal excretion, which decreases BAs accumulation in the systemic circulation and liver. Our data indicate that DMF may be beneficial for further testing in human fibrosing cholangiopathies. Furthermore, we addressed a significant impairment of secondary BA formation by the DDC diet due to a reduced abundance of *Bacteroides* microbial phyla in the gut by direct toxicity of the compound.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary materials. Individual values are available upon request.

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Figs. S1–S10: <https://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28518305.v1>.

Supplemental Tables S1–S10: <https://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28518203.v1>.

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DISCLOSURES

No conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, are declared by the authors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

S.M. conceived and designed research; H.L., E.D., D.F.M., J.C., J.M., J.P., I.P., M.B., L.S., A.S., R.K., L.J., M.U., P.P., S.M., and M.H. performed experiments; H.L., E.D., D.F.M., J.M., J.P., P.H., P.N., I.P., P.P., S.M., and M.H. analyzed data; P.H., P.N., P.P., S.M., and M.H. interpreted results of experiments; H.L., E.D., J.C., J.P., I.P., M.B.,

L.S., A.S., R.K., L.J., and M.U. prepared figures; H.L. drafted manuscript; J.P., P.H., P.N., P.P., S.M., and M.H. edited and revised manuscript; H.L., E.D., D.F.M., J.M., J.P., P.H., P.N., I.P., M.U., S.M., and M.H. approved final version of manuscript.

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